

The Nord-Pas de Calais coalfield, a big artifact to preserve

**BASSIN
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NORD - PAS DE CALAIS
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Definitions of an « artifact »

The Oxford English Dictionary :

« anything made by human art and workmanship ; an artificial product »

The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy

« an object that has been intentionally made or produced for a certain purpose »

The former Nord-Pas de Calais coalfield

1720-1990 : *the Coalfield used to be a big artifact made for a unique purpose : mining production*

The historical impact of the coalmining activity

Discovery of coal in 1720 in the North-East area of the Coalfield

- ✓ 43 mining concessions for a total perimeter of 140 000 ha (1/6 of the Nord-Pas de Calais region)
- ✓ 600 pits sunk ; in 1945 109 pits ; 1991 none
- ✓ 340 tips (some remain under the shape of former railway tracks)
- ✓ 100 000 km of underground galleries
- ✓ 67 000 coalmining housing estate in 2011 (with a peak in 1967: 120 000)
- ✓ 218 000 coalmining employees in 1947
- ✓ Today, 1 200 000 inhabitants and 160 local authorities

THE NORD-PAS DE CALAIS COALFIELD HERITAGE

SURVEY OF THE PROPERTIES OF THE NATIONAL COALMINING COMPANY IN THE NORD-PAS DE CALAIS IN 1969

4 000 ha of tips & brownfield

17 600 ha of fields & woods

1 600 km of railway tracks

11 police barracks

120 000 housing estate

Social and education facilities

11 hospitals, clinics & maternity homes

120 water pumps

91 presbyteries, **51** churches & chapels

29 stadiums, **24** sport facilities, **12** football fields

20 schools of domestic science

... A PROGRESSIVE SPLIT

1990 : *the end of mining production*
Coalfield provoked the dismantling of
the big artifact, and environmental,
urban, social economic shocks

An environmental and urban shock

- A large quantity of brownfield at the regional scale:**10 000 ha in 1983**, massively concentrated in the Coalbasin : 7 500 ha (including **5 000 coalmining brownfield**)
- Contamination of soils
- Geological disorders (subsidence)
- Hydraulic disorders.
- Urban sprawling is threatening natural resources
- Very uncomfortable housing
- A strong proportion of social housing

A social and economic severe shock

Unemployment rate in the Coalfield in 2009

Taux de chômage (INSEE)

(source : INSEE 2009)

Today : the actual state of conservation and protection of the coalfield heritage is the result of 30-year regeneration policies

From massive and quantitative brownfield regeneration policies (1989-2000) to more holistic approaches (2000-2014)

Regeneration policies led in the Nord-Pas de Calais

1982-1983: a test is launched on 4 experimental brownfield sites

1984-1988: experimental « industrial brownfield redevelopment » program in the 1st National and Regional Development Pact

1989-1993: acceleration of the process. Creation of a specific governmental tool : the Etablissement Public Foncier Nord-Pas de Calais – the Land Regeneration Agency

1994-1999: boosting of the redevelopment policy (combination between « environmental regeneration » led by the E.P.F and 100% funded by the State/Regional Council and E.R.D.F. and « finalized regeneration » led by local communities and 50 to 80% funded)

2000-2006: « brownfield » extended to the wider concept of « degraded spaces »; regeneration policy more targeted ; brownfields to be integrated in holistic development strategies

2007-2013 : specific measures of the National and Regional Development Pact devoted to the land, urban and environmental regeneration of former industrial basins

Concrete achievements

- Since 1972, **45 000 coalmining housing estate** have been renovated (including all the concerned roads)
- Since the 1980's, more than **7 000 ha of brownfield** have been regenerated (1 770 ha of tips to be purchased by the General Councils as « Sensitive Natural Spaces »). Major heritage sites treated.
- **A good supply of available land**, for employment and residential uses.
- **Between 1990 and 2005, employment in the Coalfield has increased: (+3,5%)**
- **Diversified economic sectors** have been developed
- **The demographic decline** has slowed down.
- A good location of the Coalfield : **easy access by the transportation networks.**
- Development of **large-scale projects** as the Louvre-Lens
- The development/reinforcement of **central urban functions** in Valenciennes and Lens for example (impact of university, of Louvre-Lens etc)

The Coalfield heritage today

An evolving cultural landscape (UNESCO)

- *Defined as « the combined works of nature and of man » (§ 47 of the World Heritage operational guidelines)*
- *Illustrative of the evolution of human society and settlement over time, under the influence of the physical constraints and/or opportunities presented by their natural environment and of successive social, economic and cultural forces, both internal and external »*

The Nord-Pas de Calais Coalfield evolving cultural landscape

- **A perfectly legible landscape** offering the different « layers » of human activities

- **A complete landscape** : technical, social, urban, environmental, cultural heritage.

- **A long and breakless** chronology (19th et 20th centuries) and events having international scope

- *“ It represents a major symbolic place of the workers’ condition and their solidarity, from the 1850s to 1990. They are testimony to the dissemination of the ideals of worker unionism and socialism.” ICOMOS*

*The 10-year UNESCO nomination
process gave birth to a new big artefact
→ The World Heritage Site*

The Nord-Pas de Calais Coalfield on the List of World Heritage

- 87 local communities
- 353 objects
- 3 900 hectares
- 25% of the remaining cultural heritage

- 17 collieries or significant vestiges of collieries,
- 21 headgear structures,
- 51 spoil heaps,
- 54 kilometres of former railway tracks and 3 railway stations,
- 124 estates of miners' housing,
- 45 schools and leisure facilities,
- 17 churches and chapels,
- 21 health facilities,
- head offices of 3 mining companies
- 4,000 hectares of landscape...

The World Heritage Site can be perceived as the combination of several artefacts at 3 levels

→ The different typologies

→ Mining quarters

→ Big landscapes

1st level: The different typologies

Technical heritage

Pits and headframes

Fosse du 9-9bis, Oignies

Fosse Delloye, Lewarde

Fosse n°3bis la Société de Lens à Liévin

Fosse Dutemple, Valenciennes

Fosse n°9, Roost-Warendin

Spoil hips and transport networks

Terril n°97 à Méricourt

Terril du Fort Louis, Harnes

Terril d'Estevelles

Cavalier à Haisnes-lez-la Bassée

La gare de Lens

Social heritage

67 000 coalmining housing estate

Terraced rows of miners' houses (1820-1890)

Coron des 120, à Anzin/ Valenciennes

Detached housing (1890-1939)

Cité du 10 à Sains-en-Gohelle

Cité de la Ferronnière à Douai,

garden city developments (1904-1939)

Cité du Pinson, Raismes

Cité de la Clochette, Douai

Apartment blocks (1950-1960)

Cité de la Nouvelle Solitude à Vieux-Condé

Camus haut, Annay-sous-Lens

Education / Churches / Social and sanitary facilities

School in Arenberg

School, cité du Bouvier, Avion

Village Hall, Douchy-les-Mines

Village Hall, Arenberg

Swimming pool, Bruay-la-Buissière

Stadium, Bully-les-Mines

Immaterial heritage

Work

Avion

Social
struggles
and
strikes

Strikes, 1936

Miner's status, 1945

Memorial, Liévin

Union House, Lens, 1922

Sociability

Immigration

29 different nationalities

Belgian,
Kabylian,
Polish,
Italian,
Algerian,
Moroccan

Etc....

Lens, 1930

Lesquin, 1976

15 exceptional mining micro-landscapes including mining-quarters

2nd level: mining quarter

Fosse n°11-19 et cité des Provinces à Loos-en-Gohelle et Lens

3rd level: 16 « big landscapes »

Fosse 11-19 à Loos-en-Gohelle

Terril des Pinchonvalles à Avion

Depuis le terril n°14 d'Auchel

Zoom on the exceptional coalmining landscape of Pit 9/9 bis in Oignies

Hôtel de ville, Carvin

*Fosse 9-9bis,
Oignies*

*Cité de la forêt,
Libercourt*

*Eglise Saint-Henri
Libercourt*

Cité Saint-Paul, Carvin

*Fosse n°2,
Oignies*

*Cité Cornuault,
Evin-Malmaison*

*Terrils 101, 205 et 84,
Drocourt, Rouvroy*

*Eglise Saint-Louis
Rouvroy*

Cité Bruno, Dourges

*Résidence de la Motte
Rouvroy*

*Cité Foch, Hénin-
Beaumont*

*Terril 87,
Hénin-Beaumont/
Dourges*

*Cité Crombez,
Noyelles-Godault*

Pit 9/9 bis in Oignies

The regeneration project of the pit 9-9 bis

Investment budget : 25 million euros
Operating budget : 2,5 million euros/year

Economic development

Development of technological and innovating tertiary activities connected to logistics (the Campus of logistics ; the EURALOGISTIC regional pole of competitiveness)

Business tourism : incentive, seminars, symposiums etc.

Touristic facilities : a hotel and a restaurant ; a reception hall ; catering

Culture : the « chain » of musical practices

An education programme to reinforce musical practices

Development of facilities for schools

Creation of a master class

A new offer of cultural products and places to develop the attractiveness of the site:

- **concert halls and « café-concert » (a café with musicians and singers)**
- **Artistic and research activities** : recording and rehearsal studios, guest artists (residence), a resource centre, a research centre on sound
- **The « sound gallery »** , as a n important factor to introduce the public to musical practice

Industrial heritage : to tell the history of the site (exhibition), with a focus on land-planning issues

PHASE 1

2006-2010

Regenerating the site

- **2008 : Connecting the site to the A1 highway, pedestrian paths, car-parks, networks : 1,8 million €**
- **2009 : Build the first tertiary building : 2 millions €**
- **Regenerate and improve the quality of external spaces : 1,5 million € (ended in 2010)**
- **Use the architectural references of the site for the design of contemporary buildings**

PHASE 2
2010-2012

**Making the site attractive
for visitors and investors**

**ERDF (European Regional
Development Fund) 2007-2013**

3,6 millions €

THE METAPHONE

Concert hall + Congress hall

Peau sonore

Structure peau

Salle de concert

Accueil / Foyer

To create an exhibition about industrial heritage and a café

Plan mezzanine

EXPOSITION PATRIMONIALE

Plan RDC

EXPOSITION PATRIMONIALE

GALERIE SONORE

Creation of a hotel and a restaurant (2* plus)

Seminar rooms

Live in a park !

Site du 9/9 bis, OIGNIES

Construction de 35 maisons individuelles passives

Ech. 1/1500

PHASE 3

2012-2014

**Developing the chain of musical practices
and opening the site to the public**

**ERDF 2007-2013 (axe 4 priorité 5) :
3,6 millions €**

Music, as a cultural catalyst : since 2005, yearly brass band festival : *les Rutilants* in 9/9 bis, Oignies

De la fosse Delloye...

Boosters of
a new
ambition

...au centre historique minier

... à la fabrique à images

De Wallers – Arenberg...

A positive
perception of
industrial
cultural heritage

De Loos en Gohelle ...

...au pôle de référence du développement
durable et Culture commune
« fabrique théâtrale »

**The coalmining heritage
development strategy :
The Management Plan**

What is at stake in the Management Plan ?

- Giving guarantees that the universal and exceptional value will be preserved in the long term
- Combining integrity and authenticity with evolution
- Cultural heritage as a powerful catalyst of a change of image and of urban, architectural and landscape quality
- Reinforcing technical and financial management

The Management Plan

Legal & reglementary procedures to protect, preserve, develop & manage heritage sites

1. Protection
2. Planning

Contracts

1. The UNESCO Coalfield heritage Charter adopted by the Association of Coalmining local communities
2. Agreements signed with owners and managers of exceptional buildings, housing estate, tips
3. Agreements signed with 8 intermunicipal structures

The programme of action : 11 strategic fields

ZOOM on the importance of **ART** in our
ART-EFACT
strategic field 6. « To encourage
cultural projects having a link with
mining heritage »

Artists in residence
promenade
du jardin des souhaits
bricolés, cité des
Electriciens à Bruay-la-
Buisnière, 2011
**Compagnie des pas
Perdus**

Art Deco swimming pool and stadium
in Bruay-la-Buisnière

"Water Born"
contemporary dance
show, 2007, **Carolyn
Carlson**

Geo-poetic path by
Yann KERSALE,
renowned « light
designer », 2011 :
Béthune, Regional
Capital of Culture

2012 : Land art "*Mine d'art en sentier*"

This project gathered 11 international artists who created temporary works inspired by mining and miners, dotting an 8-kilometre path, in the Scarpe/Escaut regional park (Eastern part of the Coalfield)

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THANK
YOU!

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